

Supplementary Material 2

Do Specialist Butterflies Perceive Resources Differently Than Generalists?

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1. Butterfly Tracking Study

1.1. Average Flight Time

Table S1. Average time spent on flying recorded during the butterfly tracking study. Original model contained four explanatory variables: species (*Phengaris teleius* and *Polyommatus icarus*), sex (females and males), locality (Selevenj and Ludaš) and mowing regime (mown and unmown meadow).

Parameter estimates	Estimate ± SE	Z value	P value
Intercept	2.462 ± 0.134	18.376	< 0.001
Sex (male)	0.688 ± 0.158	4.361	< 0.001
Mowing regime (unmown meadow)	-0.228 ± 0.059	-3.847	< 0.001

Estimates of response	Rate ± SE
Females at Mown meadow	11.73 ± 1.57
Males at Mown meadow	23.35 ± 2.55
Females at Unmown meadow	9.34 ± 1.18
Males at Unmown meadow	18.58 ± 1.78

Contrasts	Ratio ± SE	Z ratio	P value
Females at mown meadow / Males at mown meadow	0.502 ± 0.079	-4.361	< 0.001
Females at mown meadow / Females at unmown meadow	1.257 ± 0.075	3.847	0.001
Females at mown meadow / Males at unmown meadow	0.632 ± 0.105	-2.760	0.029
Males at mown meadow / Females at unmown meadow	2.501 ± 0.427	5.370	< 0.001
Males at mown meadow / Males at unmown meadow	1.257 ± 0.075	3.847	0.001
Females at unmown meadow / Males at unmown meadow	0.502 ± 0.793	-4.361	< 0.001

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. Variance of the individual variation (random effect) was 0.491 ± 0.701 based on 459 observations of 89 individuals. Poisson mixed model was fitted using *lme4*, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package in R.

1.2. Average Interaction Time

Table S2. Average time spent on interactions during the butterfly tracking study. Original model contained four explanatory variables: species (*Phengaris teleius* and *Polyommatus icarus*), sex (females and males), locality (Selevenj and Ludaš) and mowing regime (mown and unmown meadow).

Parameter estimates	Estimate ± SE	Z vlaue	P value
Intercept	2.750 ± 0.270	10.183	< 0.001
Sex (male)	-0.696 ± 0.262	-2.660	0.008
Species (<i>P. icarus</i>)	-0.595 ± 0.338	-1.761	0.078
Mowing regime (unmown meadow)	-0.572 ± 0.197	-2.900	0.004

Estimates of response	Rate ± SE
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow	15.64 ± 4.22
Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow	7.80 ± 1.85
Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at mown meadow	4.30 ± 1.53
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	8.83 ± 1.82
Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	4.40 ± 0.73
Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at unmown meadow	2.43 ± 0.72

Contrasts	Estimates of response	Rate ± SE	P value
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow	2.007 ± 0.525	2.660	0.135
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at mown meadow	3.639 ± 1.308	3.595	0.008
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	1.772 ± 0.35	2.900	0.073
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	3.556 ± 1.176	3.836	0.003
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at unmown meadow	6.449 ± 2.577	4.664	0.000
Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at mown meadow	1.814 ± 0.613	1.761	0.647
Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	0.883 ± 0.287	0.383	1.000
Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	1.772 ± 0.35	2.900	0.073
Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at unmown meadow	3.213 ± 1.215	3.087	0.042
Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at mown meadow / Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	0.487 ± 0.204	1.714	0.678
Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	0.977 ± 0.395	0.057	1.000
Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at mown meadow / Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at unmown meadow	1.772 ± 0.35	2.900	0.073
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow / Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow	2.007 ± 0.525	2.660	0.135
Females of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow / Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at unmown meadow	3.639 ± 1.308	3.595	0.008
Males of <i>P. teleius</i> at unmown meadow / Males of <i>P. icarus</i> at unmown meadow	1.814 ± 0.613	1.761	0.647

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. Variance of the individual variation (random effect) was 0.709 ± 0.842 based on 137 observations of 61 individuals. Poisson mixed model was fitted using *lme4*, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package in R.

Table S3. Average time spent on interactions during the butterfly tracking study. Original model included significant variables from Table S2 and an additional variable to differentiate interspecific (different species) and intraspecific (same species) interactions.

Parameter estimates	Estimate ± SE	Z vlaue	P value
Intercept	0.617 ± 0.252	2.449	0.014
Interaction (intraspecific)	1.330 ± 0.235	5.668	< 0.001
Estimates of response	Rate ± SE		
Interspecific interactions	1.85 ± 0.47		
Intraspecific interactions	7.01 ± 1.06		
Contrast	Ratio ± SE	Z ratio	P value
Interspecific interactions / Intraspecific interactions	0.264 ± 0.062	-5.668	< 0.001

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. Variance of the individual variation (random effect) was 0.91 ± 0.95 based on 98 observations of 48 individuals. Poisson mixed model was fitted using *lme4*, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package in R.

Table S4. Comparison of average interspecific interaction times for individuals of the same sexes in contrast to individuals of different sexes.

Parameter estimates	Estimate ± SE	Z vlaue	P value
Intercept	2.260 ± 0.178	12.724	< 0.001
Same sex	-0.791 ± 0.148	-5.329	< 0.001
Estimates	Rate ± SE		
Different sex	9.58 ± 1.70		
Same sex	4.34 ± 0.82		
Contrast	Ratio ± SE	Z ratio	P value
Different sex / Same sex	2.21 ± 0.33	5.329	< 0.001

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. Variance of the individual variation (random effect) was 0.895 ± 0.946 based on 67 observations of 37 individuals. Poisson mixed model was fitted using *lme4*, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package in R.

1.3. Average Feeding Time

Table S5. Average time that *Phengaris teleius* butterflies spent on feeding during the tracking study. Original model contained four explanatory variables: plant (*Sanguisorba officinalis* and other Compositae plants), sex (females and males), locality (Selevenj and Ludaš) and mowing regime (mown and unmown meadow).

Parameter estimates	Estimate	Z value	P value
Intercept	2.940 ± 0.172	17.048	< 0.001
Plant (Compositae)	1.384 ± 0.179	7.709	< 0.001
Sex (male)	-0.464 ± 0.264	-1.758	0.079
Interaction term (Compositae × male)	-0.448 ± 0.226	-1.981	0.047

Estimates of response	Rate ± SE
Females on <i>S. officinalis</i>	18.9 ± 3.26
Females on Compositae plants	75.5 ± 16.68
Males on <i>S. officinalis</i>	11.9 ± 2.38
Males on Compositae plants	30.3 ± 6.16

Contrasts	Ratio ± SE	Z ratio	P value
Females on <i>S. officinalis</i> / Female on Compositae	0.251 ± 0.045	-7.709	< 0.001
Females on <i>S. officinalis</i> / Males on <i>S. officinalis</i>	1.591 ± 0.420	1.758	0.294
Females on <i>S. officinalis</i> / Males on Compositae	0.624 ± 0.166	-1.774	0.286
Females on Compositae / Males on <i>S. officinalis</i>	6.352 ± 1.899	6.183	< 0.001
Females on Compositae / Males on Compositae	2.491 ± 0.751	3.027	0.013
Males on <i>S. officinalis</i> / Males on Compositae	0.392 ± 0.053	-6.910	< 0.001

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. Variance of the individual variation (random effect) was 0.710 ± 0.843 based on 130 observation of 47 individuals. Poisson mixed model was fitted using *lme4*, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package in R.

1.4. Average Resting Time

Table S6. Average time spent on resting during the tracking study. Original model contained four explanatory variables: species (*Phengaris teleius* and *Polyommatus icarus*), sex (females and males), locality (Selevenj and Ludaš) and mowing regime (mown and unmown meadow).

Parameter estimates	Estimate ± SE	Z value	P value
Intercept	2.143 ± 0.316	6.783	< 0.001
Sex (male)	-1.135 ± 0.593	-1.915	0.055
Locality (Selevenj)	-0.459 ± 0.427	-1.074	0.283
Interaction term (male × Selevenj)	2.021 ± 0.712	2.839	0.004

Estimates of response	Rate ± SE
Females at Ludaš Lake	8.52 ± 2.69
Females at Selevenj Sand	5.39 ± 1.55
Males at Ludaš Lake	2.74 ± 1.37
Males at Selevenj Sand	13.07 ± 3.52

Contrasts	Ratio ± SE	Z ratio	P value
Females at Ludaš / Females at Selevenj	1.582 ± 0.676	1.074	0.706
Females at Ludaš / Males at Ludaš	3.111 ± 1.844	1.915	0.222
Females at Ludaš / Males at Selevenj	0.652 ± 0.271	-1.030	0.732
Females at Selevenj / Males at Ludaš	1.966 ± 1.137	1.169	0.647
Females at Selevenj / Males at Selevenj	0.412 ± 0.163	-2.247	0.111
Males at Ludaš / Males at Selevenj	0.210 ± 0.119	-2.744	0.031

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. Variance of the individual variation (random effect) was 1.315 ± 1.147 based on 155 observations of 56 individuals. Poisson mixed model was fitted using *lme4*, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package in R.

2. Mark Release Recapture Study

2.1. Intersexual Differences in Plant Preferences

Table S7. Intersexual differences in feeding plants of *Phengaris teleius* grouped in three classes based on phylogeny and sample size.

Parameter estimates	Estimate ± SE	Z value	P value
Compositae	0.308 ± 0.219	1.404	0.160
Other plants	0.693 ± 0.327	2.118	0.034
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	-0.383 ± 0.117	-3.265	0.001
Estimates of response	Probability ± SE		
Compositae	0.576 ± 0.054		
Other plants	0.667 ± 0.073		
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	0.405 ± 0.028		
Contrasts	Odds ratio ± SE	Z ratio	P value
Compositae / Other plants	0.681 ± 0.268	-0.976	0.592
Compositae / <i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	1.997 ± 0.497	2.778	0.015
Other plants / <i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	2.934 ± 1.020	3.096	0.006

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. GLM binomial model was fitted using R base function, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package.

Table S8. Intersexual differences in resting plants of *Phengaris teleius* grouped in four classes based on phylogeny and sample size.

Coefficients	Estimate	Z value	P value
Compositae	0.257 ± 0.139	1.854	0.064
Other plants	0.069 ± 0.166	4.150	0.678
Poales	0.376 ± 0.121	3.121	0.002
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	-0.411 ± 0.086	-4.796	< 0.001
Estimates	Probability estimate		
Compositae	0.564 ± 0.034		
Other plants	0.517 ± 0.041		
Poales	0.593 ± 0.029		
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	0.399 ± 0.021		
Contrasts	Odds ration	Z ratio	P value
Compositae / Other plants	1.207 ± 0.261	8.700	0.821
Compositae / Poales	0.888 ± 0.163	-6.470	0.917
Compositae / <i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	1.952 ± 0.318	4.098	< 0.001
Other plants / Poales	0.735 ± 0.151	-1.497	0.439
Other plants / <i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	1.617 ± 0.302	2.568	0.050
Poales / <i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	2.198 ± 0.325	5.323	< 0.001

Statistically significant *P* values are shown in bold. GLM binomial model was fitted using R base function, while estimates of response and contrasts are calculated in *emmeans* package.

3. Overview of the Plant Usage

Table S9. The list of plant species and other objects used by *Phengaris teleius* and *Polyommatus icarus* butterflies for feeding and resting, with percentages of their use shown.

Plant/object	Mark-release-recapture				Butterfly tracking study					
	<i>Phengaris teleius</i>		<i>Phengaris teleius</i>		<i>Phengaris teleius</i>		<i>Phengaris teleius</i>		<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	
	(females)	(males)	(females)	(males)	(females)	(males)	(females)	(males)	(males)	(males)
	Feed (%)	Rest (%)	Feed (%)	Rest (%)						
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	77.83	53.90	61.31	36.78	90.11	70.43	43.66	40.48		
<i>Serratula tinctoria</i>	14.78	7.95	18.59	11.00	8.79	11.30	43.66	52.38	51.43	38.89
<i>Epilobium</i> sp.	3.39	0.48	3.52	2.30						
<i>Knautia integrifolia</i>	0.43		4.02	0.33						
<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	0.43	4.61	2.51	6.08		3.48	12.68		2.86	11.11
<i>Stenactis annua</i>	0.43	0.79	2.51	0.66						
<i>Viccia cracca</i>	0.43	0.16	2.01	0.16						
<i>Trifolium pratensis</i>			1.51	0.16						
Fabaceae	0.43		0.50							
<i>Campanula glomerata</i>	0.43		0.50							
<i>Achillea asplenifolia</i>		0.64	1.01	1.31	1.10			4.76	5.71	
<i>Plantago maritima</i>	0.43	1.91	0.50	2.46		2.61				
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>			0.50							
<i>Stachis palustris</i>			0.50							
<i>Lathyrus tuberosus</i>			0.50							
Snail shell	0.43	1.59		3.28						
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>									37.14	5.56
Poaceae		8.43		13.63		5.22		2.38		16.67
<i>Mollinia</i> sp.		7.15		10.67						
<i>Festuca ovina</i>										
<i>Phragmites communis</i>		1.27		1.15						
<i>Carex</i> sp.		0.16		0.16		0.87				
<i>Genista tinctoria</i>		0.16		0.33						
<i>Galium verum</i>		3.18		3.12						
<i>Equisetum</i> sp.		2.07		1.64		0.87				
<i>Holoschoenus vulgaris</i>		1.27		1.15						
<i>Silene vulgaris</i>		0.64		0.49						
<i>Ononis spinosa</i>		1.75		0.66		0.87				16.67
<i>Linum</i>										
<i>perenae/austriacum</i>		0.16								
<i>Cirsium canum</i>				0.16						
<i>Prunella officinalis</i>				0.33						
Other Compositae		0.32							2.86	
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>		0.32				2.61				
<i>Salvia</i> sp.		0.16								
Apiaceae		0.16		0.33						
<i>Lepidium cartilagineum</i>										5.56
<i>Medicago sativa</i>										5.56
Dry plant organs		0.64		0.81		1.74				
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i> leaf		0.16		0.33						